

RE-USE OF CARBON FIBRES IN HIGH VALUE MOULDING COMPOUNDS & PRE-PREGS

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SUMMARY

High quality carbon fibres recovered from fluidised bed and pyrolysis processes have been incorporated in bulk & sheet moulding compounds and prepreg composite materials. Various influencing factors have been investigated including fibre length, filler types and levels and mat binder types and levels. Demonstrator materials have shown excellent mechanical properties.

Keywords: Carbon Fibre, Recycling, Automotive Applications, Fibre Alignment, Moulding Compounds

INTRODUCTION

Interest in the sustainability of carbon fibre structures is growing alongside the increasing use of these materials. The benefits of carbon reinforced composites in terms of weight saving and performance increase for aerospace, automotive and industrial structures is now widely accepted. Legislative factors such as end-of-life regulations are creating the need to reduce landfill of automotive structures. Unless an efficient recycling route can be established for carbon based composites their future use will be limited. As a result, recycling of carbon fibres is of considerable benefit to both fibre manufacturers and original equipment manufacturers.

This paper reports work undertaken as part of a research project to address both the recovery of fibres and the issues surrounding reuse of the fibres in high value parts. Various fibre recovery processes have been reported [1] but little published data is available on the use of these fibres in structural composites (the use of carbon fibres in milled form or in electromagnetic shielding applications has not been considered here)

The recovery processes considered as part of this work include a thermal fluidised bed recovery process [2] and a developmental supercritical fluids recovery process [3]. The fluidised bed process is highly tolerant of contamination in the form of paint, sandwich cores and metallic inserts and could easily be converted to a continuous process. In this process a reduction in fibre properties is observed - although the modulus is practically unchanged [4], single filament tensile strength is reduced to around 50 to 75% of the virgin fibre value. Fibres recovered from the supercritical fluids process have properties virtually indistinguishable from virgin fibres, but the process requires greater attention

to recycle preparation and sorting. Fibres are stripped of their sizing but testing has not shown any significant fibre:matrix adhesion issues when epoxy polymer is used. Other polymers, particularly thermoplastics, may require additional fibre treatment [5].

In this work we propose a lifecycle for carbon fibre as shown in Figure 1 where scrap carbon fibre is produced as a result of in-process waste (e.g. prepreg offcuts during series production) or end of life high performance parts (e.g. NCF and prepreg aerospace parts and high performance industrial parts). Clearly these scrap streams have high intrinsic value and also incur a significant disposal cost.

Figure 1 Proposed carbon fibre lifecycle

Several barriers can be identified which currently limit production of recycled carbon fibre composites in any form: point-of-production waste identification and separation is an important step in the creation of a viable recycling strategy. Transportation of production waste / end-of-life (EOL) parts to a central recycling facility is a similar difficulty. Further barriers are the technological issues presented by actual recovery of the fibres, manufacture of intermediate materials (if required) such as tow or mat and manufacture of recovered fibre composites raw materials such as prepreps and moulding compounds.

Our aim in this work is to address the final three of these barriers. The fundamental concern with the reuse of recovered fibres is taking fibres in a fluffy form and transforming them into a form which can be impregnated with polymer. The chosen development route is to investigate the potential of thermoset moulding compounds and prepreps as the most viable material for medium term use of recovered fibres. Our primary area of interest is in medium length (5mm to 50mm) fibres. Target mechanical properties are similar to glass fibre based moulding compounds typically used in automotive applications.

FIBRE RECOVERY

Fibre preparation

Efficient preparation of the material prior to recovery is an important step in recycling. The critical issues can be summarised as follows;

- Attainment of target fibre length – (longer fibres generally give higher mechanical properties whereas recovery systems generally favour shorter)
- Fibre length distribution – consistency of length
- Dust production – maximum incidence of usable fibres
- Throughput & running cost
- Efficient feeding of material into recovery system

Evidently the fibre length will have to be reduced from the continuous or semi-continuous lengths encountered in scrap as it is not practical (at least at the present time) to envisage recovery and subsequent reuse of very long fibres. Hence there exists the option to reduce length prior to or following fibre recovery. For this work we have investigated length reduction prior to recycling as the more promising of the two choices. A major reason for this choice is the fact that all materials can be treated similarly whether end of life parts or scrap prepreg. Prepreg process scrap constitutes a significant volume of waste material, which in some processes can be 40% of the material used. Use of this waste stream has numerous advantages; the material is traceable with respect to fibre type, the material is clean and planar. It can be seen that in high enough volumes and with the correct infrastructure in place, prepreg process scrap could justify a bespoke comminution process.

Fibre length is an important factor as mechanical properties of the composites produced from the recovered fibres are generally higher if the fibre length is long - according to some authors, at least 100 times the critical length. The actual fibre length required for full retention of properties is dependent on the ratio of the moduli of the constituents and fibre volume fraction.

This work focuses on the granulating process; predominantly for scrap prepreg, although much of the data is also valid for EOL parts (as the interlaminar properties tend to be so much lower than the in-plane, 3D composites tend to first break into laminae upon granulation). Six types of prepreg have been granulated to represent a wide range of possible input materials. Three of the prepregs are woven; two lightweight materials with different unit cell sizes and one heavy material, and three of the prepregs are non-crimp; a unidirectional (UD) and $\pm 45^\circ$ and a $\pm 45/0^\circ$ tri-axial. Granulator speed was held constant but 5 granulator screen sizes were used, with all materials were tested at all screen sizes.

Sieving is a rapid characterisation process used to determine mass fractions at various particle sizes. The disadvantage of the method for high aspect ratio particles is that it does not provide a measure of true particle size. Due to its ease of use however, it does provide rapid comparative measurements. An optical method has been developed in order to characterise the actual fibre lengths and the results compared to both wet and dry sieving. Use of the optical method allows “calibration” of the sieving, such that sieving can return more accurate data on the true fibre length distribution.

Method

Six prepreg materials were supplied by the Advanced Composites Group with specifications as shown in Table 1. The materials had a variety of resin systems and fibre types but the main determining factor in their selection was the weave style (Figure 2)

Table 1 Prepreg data – materials supplied by Advanced Composites Group Ltd

Designation	Resin type	Fibre type	Areal mass (gsm)	Resin weight	Key
1 Woven	LTM110	3K HS	199	43%	LW
2 Woven – large unit cell	VTM264	12K HS	193	42%	LUCW
3 Woven – heavy	VTM264FRB	12K HS	660	38%	HW
4 Unidirectional	MTM49-3	12K HM	150	38%	UD
5 Non-crimp ± 45	MTM28	12K HS	600	42%	NCF
6 Non-crimp tri-axial	MTM58FRB	24K HS	900	Unknown	TRIAX

Figure 2 Schematic of prepregs tested showing relative weave styles, unit cell size and thickness (25mm x 25mm shown in all cases)

A Zerma GSL180/300 slow speed granulator has been employed in this work. The machine has three sets of 10 knives arranged in a v-pattern on a rotor diameter of 180mm. The knives cut against two fixed anvils arranged on opposite sides of the cutting chamber. Cutting width is 300mm and cutting speed is 150rpm. Prepreg materials were unrolled, cut into 1m x 300mm sections and heated in a hot air oven at 120°C until fully cured. The backing paper was then removed and the stacked prepregs were bandsawn into 300x150mm sections to allow efficient feeding into the granulator. Granulator meshes were used as-supplied by Zerma at the following sizes; 6mm, 8mm, 15mm, 20mm and 25mm. Approximately 10kg of each prepreg was cured and prepared for granulating allowing approx 1kg loads to be granulated at each mesh size. Output material was collected in polythene bags for storage and further analysis. Dust extraction was employed in the vicinity of the material inlet and during material transfer.

Granulated materials were sieved using an Endecotts Octagon 2000 shaker with 200mm diameter sieves to BS 410-1:2000. Sieve mesh apertures were 0.6mm, 1mm, 2mm,

4mm, 8mm, and 11.2mm. Sieving was carried out at maximum amplitude for 10 minutes. Representative samples of ~100g were taken from the 1kg of granulated material. Sieving and data presentation was undertaken according to the method given in 1796-1:1989.

Optical characterisation was performed by spreading samples obtained from the sieving process on a flatbed scanner and scanning at 300dpi. Efforts were made to ensure that the particles were not touching. Images were imported into UTHSCSA ImageTool V3.0 software and thresholded to convert from greyscale to black and white. Objects were found and characterised automatically according to the internal algorithms. The resulting object data was exported to a spreadsheet for further analysis.

The heavy woven and unidirectional prepregs were selected for optical analysis to allow calibration of the sieving process and therefore to determine true fibre length distributions contained within a given sieve size. The retained samples from the sieving analysis were analysed according to the method outlined above. Where samples were too large to analyse the entire mass, a representative sample was taken. Typically the contents of the 11.2, 8, 4 and 2mm sieves were analysed in their entirety whereas the smaller sieves required representative samples to be taken. Accuracy of measurements for the dust was considered to be inaccurate and was not considered. The results presented therefore do not include the “receiver” (i.e. the material remaining having passed through all sieves) proportion.

Results

Figure 3 shows a clear trend for the heavy woven prepreg with similar gradients for all screen sizes. All materials followed a similar power law relationship. The heavier materials (HW, TRIAX and NCF) tend towards smaller pieces (greater cumulative undersize values). The unidirectional material is unusual in that it is lightweight yet retains a small size distribution; this is explained by the fact that it is the sole single-layer material in the group, the others having either woven or stitched layers. The other two lightweight materials (LW and LUCW) have a large size distribution in all cases. The adjustment offered by changing the granulator screen appears to give a well-defined and controllable method of adjusting the size distribution of each material. It was clear from this work that the materials fell into two categories; the unidirectional was particularly poorly characterised by the sieving due to the high aspect ratio of the pieces whereas the remaining materials were broadly similar. UD and HW were selected for further analysis.

An assumption implicit in the data reduction employed is that the major axis length of the segment is equal to the fibre length. In the case of unidirectional materials the assumption is valid but it may not hold for other materials. Whilst the mean fibre length can be calculated for each sieve sample, it is most useful to use sieving data to weight the sample area according to the proportion of the total contained in a given sieve. For instance, for the HW material 32% of the total is contained in the 2mm sieve. Therefore any data obtained by optical methods must be weighted by a factor $1/0.32$. A frequency analysis of the major axis length data has also been conducted and normalised. It is clear from these results that the sieving is measuring the minor axis length with good accuracy. The mean aspect ratio for the UD is 10.8:1, which implies that lengths determined through sieving can be multiplied by 10.8 to give true fibre lengths. The aspect ratio for the woven material is more interesting: Larger pieces have an aspect

ratio of 1.6-1.7 but this value increases towards smaller segment sizes. This is due to through-thickness fragmentation allowing the unit cell of the material to breakdown and allowing thinner pieces of material to break off. This effect is observed with all the materials apart from UD and makes calibration of the sieving data more difficult.

The results are easier to interpret when optimal targets are defined on the basis of value (e.g. minimisation of dust fraction or selection of a range of fibre lengths. The fibre length range of interest was given in Figure 4 as 1 to 10mm. 6mm and 8mm screens are the most efficient overall for this particular assessment criterion.

Figure 3 Cumulative undersize plot for heavy woven prepreg at various granulator screen sizes

Figure 4 Useful material after granulation (~1-10mm fibre length)

Figure 5 Cumulative undersize plot for UD and HW materials (weighted optical analysis)

FIBRE ALIGNMENT

Fibre alignment is a critical factor in obtaining high mechanical properties from recovered fibres with the ultimate goal being the production of a tow-like or tape material constructed entirely from highly aligned fibres. Historically, various options have been investigated for this purpose including magnetic and electrostatic fields and convergent flows. The materials produced for the present work are made from a semi-aligned mat material which is manufactured using a modified paper-making process. A lengthy series of experiments was undertaken at Technical Fibre Products Ltd to identify the optimum processing conditions. The final mat was 10gsm with approximately 75-80% of the fibres well aligned (by visual inspection) in the machine direction. Considerable pressure is required to compact the mat to enable high fibre volume fractions (around 10-12% for vacuum only consolidation). Thickness is low so many layers are required to make parts.

Figure 6 shows the development path of aligned fibre mats. All mats were tested by stacking multiple layers of mat and infusing under vacuum with a 300gsm ACG EF6305 resin film. Fibre volume fractions are around 10%, increasing slightly with increasing alignment. The two left-hand bars are the initial products of the alignment testing at TFP. The mk2 derivative was produced by further machine optimisation and clearly had a layered structure with a layer of highly aligned fibre and a layer of random orientation stacked together. If the random layer is removed significantly higher volume fraction and mechanical properties are obtained. It was determined that areal density played a significant role in fibre formation so the third derivative had a lower mass of 10gsm and corresponding higher mechanical properties. The volume fraction of the third derivative moulded under vacuum conditions was 11.5%. Tensile strengths showed a similar trend to the modulus values.

Figure 6 Development of aligned mats showing machine direction vs. transverse direction – Tensile modulus (BS EN ISO 527-4 Type II).

MOULDING COMPOUND DEVELOPMENT

The chosen development route was to produce materials for use in existing moulding processes at costs comparable to glass-based composites but displaying increased mechanical properties. The development had three main areas – bulk moulding compounds with direct incorporation of recovered fibres into filled matrices, sheet moulding compounds and preregs based upon a partially aligned intermediate mat produced via a paper making process. Typical glass fibre based moulding compounds for automotive applications have a tensile modulus in the region of 10-15GPa and a tensile strength of 25-100MPa.

Method

Bulk moulding compounds were manufactured by the direct inclusion of recovered fibres into a mix of Advanced Composite Group EF6305 bisphenol-A epoxy resin and Omyalite 95T calcium carbonate powder.

Sheet moulding and prepreg materials were manufactured by stacking layers of 10gsm Mk3 mat as described in the previous section and pre-compacting at 40bar 5 times to increase the achievable volume fraction. Some fibre breakage is observed using this method but the benefits of increased volume fraction outweigh the disadvantages of decreased fibre length. Stacks of fibre were then impregnated using a filmed EF6305 resin at 60°C for 120 seconds prior to cooling to room temperature. Impregnation pressures were 10 bar for the vacuum only material, 15 bar for the autoclave moulding derivative and 20 bar for the higher volume fraction materials.

Developed materials

Initial screening was performed on the BMC material to identify the effects of fibre length, volume fraction (v_f) and filler type/level. Increasing fibre v_f resulted in slightly higher modulus but the strength did not increase over 10% fibre v_f . 300phr of filler was required to give acceptable flow properties. Mechanical properties were insensitive to fibre length. The final derivative (CF BMC) contained 10% fibre v_f , 12mm fibres and 1.5pbw Würtz PAT656/B3R internal mould release. A similar screening study was used for SMC/prepreg optimisation. The same EF6305 epoxy was used and was added at various levels to manufacture materials appropriate for out-of-autoclave manufacture, autoclave manufacture and press moulding (F1-F3). A further derivative was manufactured (CF SMC) to provide limited flow in the tool to give a material more like a conventional SMC. Omyalite 95T calcium carbonate filler was added to the epoxy resin at 150pbw and a resin film was made to allow impregnation in the same method as that described above. Testing showed that the binder used to manufacture the mat had a significant effect on the flow achieved in the tool and whilst high levels of flow could not be achieved, around 50% tool coverage could be used successfully.

Table 2 Developed materials

Material	Moulded v_f	Resin wt.	Key
Recovered fibre bulk moulding compound	10%	N/A	CF BMC
Vacuum only prepreg	17%	79%	F1
Autoclave prepreg	27%	67%	F2
Press prepreg	44%	51%	F3
Recovered fibre sheet moulding compound	23%	80%	CF SMC

Mechanical properties

The developed materials were moulded by the relevant process and tested according to relevant standards. The figures below show the properties of the developed materials alongside typical manufacturer's data for existing glass fibre moulding compounds. Whilst the in-plane properties of the developed materials compare very well with manufacturers data for glass-based materials, the impact strength is relatively poor due to the short fibre, un-bundled structure of the reinforcement. These results do not show the effect of the alignment present in the prepregs and SMC which approximately doubles the properties in the 1-direction compared to the random case.

Figure 7 Tensile properties of developed materials

Figure 8 Flexural properties of developed materials

Figure 9 Compressive and impact properties of developed materials

CONCLUSIONS

This work builds upon existing fibre recovery technology and looks at exploiting the recycled fibres in order to manufacture materials for a range of moulding processes. The recycled fibres can be incorporated directly into BMC products and made into an intermediate mat. This mat has a significant and useful alignment bias and has been used to manufacture four “prepreg” materials which compare favourably with existing glass-based moulding compounds.

The efficacy of granulation for prepreg comminution as preparation for fibre recovery has been shown to give predictable and repeatable performance for a wide range of input fibre architectures.

The viability of recovered fibre composites is highly dependent upon the cost of fibre recycling. Fibre production cost is unknown at this stage due to the recovery processes still being under investigation. Initial cost estimates have shown that recovered carbon fibres could be produced at a similar cost to the selling price of virgin glass fibres if processed on an industrial scale. The feasibility of the developed materials is dependant on achievement of higher alignment levels, better compaction properties, a thicker mat and highly automated manufacture.

Figure 10 Bonnet/hood manufactured out of autoclave from F1 recovered fibre prepreg

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